

SURE: A New Privacy and Utility Assessment Library for Synthetic Data

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Abstract—This paper introduces SURE, a comprehensive open-source library designed to assess the privacy risks and utility trade-offs of synthetic datasets. SURE addresses critical privacy concerns associated with synthetic data, such as the potential for individual identification through techniques like membership inference attacks. By offering a user-centric framework for evaluating both the statistical properties and privacy guarantees of synthetic data, SURE aims to balance the privacy-utility conundrum that often affects data anonymization efforts.

The library provides robust tools for data scientists and compliance officers to ensure that synthetic datasets preserve both utility and privacy for effective AI training and data analysis, while adhering to GDPR and other regulatory standards. SURE’s functionalities include statistical similarity tests, machine learning utility evaluations and privacy risk assessments, all of which are accessible through a user-friendly Python interface. Following extensive testing and validation, the finalized version of SURE will be available open-source.

Index Terms—Synthetic data, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, PETs, Privacy Engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

PwC estimates that Artificial Intelligence could contribute up to \$15.7 trillion to the global economy by 2030 [1].

The advent of generative AI tools such as ChatGPT and Midjourney based on data intensive Large Language Models [2] has led to a significant paradigm shift in both industry and society. These tools have not only revolutionized technological applications but also brought to the forefront critical and sophisticated concerns regarding user privacy and data governance, including the identification of specific individuals even within anonymized data [3]. Techniques such as model inversion can compromise sensitive data used during model training [4], while membership inference attacks can reveal if particular data, such as medical records, were part of the training dataset. The automatic decision-making capabilities of AI can further exacerbate privacy risks through unauthorized profiling of individuals.

Organizations have traditionally employed anonymization techniques like masking, aggregation, and suppression before using data to train AI models [5]. However, these methods often fail to produce fully anonymous data and significantly reduce the utility of datasets required for training robust

AI models [6]. This privacy-utility conundrum, where higher privacy results in lower utility and vice versa, necessitates innovative solutions such as Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) [6].

One prominent PET is synthetic data, which is artificially generated using AI algorithms based on real-world ‘seed’ data. Synthetic data retains the statistical properties and predictive power of the original data while not containing real personal information [7].

Synthetic data generation presents a promising solution to the privacy-utility conundrum [7]. However, the rapid advancement in this domain underscores the need for robust mechanisms to evaluate the effectiveness and, contextually, the safety of synthetic data.

To close this gap, we introduce the SURE (Synthetic Data: Utility, Regulatory compliance, and Ethical privacy) software library to provide a comprehensive framework for assessing both privacy risks and utility trade-offs associated with synthetic datasets. This library is designed to democratize access to secure and privacy-compliant data solutions across sectors, particularly in fintech, IT consulting, and system integration.

SURE seeks to develop an innovative solution that enables the responsible use of synthetic data for AI applications to solve the privacy-utility problem. This is achieved by creating an open-source library, SURE, with the primary objectives of assessing the privacy risks and reidentification threats associated with synthetic datasets, particularly in alignment with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while simultaneously ensuring that the statistical properties derived from the original dataset, essential for conducting analyses and extracting valuable insights, are preserved.

II. PRIVACY RISKS OF SYNTHETIC DATA

Privacy is a vast topic, and we have seen many discussions, innovations, and advancements especially on digital privacy since the enforcement of GDPR in 2018. However, privacy in terms of machine learning, and data science, largely remains an academic research topic, with a clear mismatch between the technical implementation and compliance requirements of privacy-enhancing technologies [8]. It is necessary to operationalize the legal requirements by commuting them into technical components. But this operation may be beyond the traditional skill set of both the AI model developers, who are

generally data scientists, and machine learning engineers, with limited privacy/legal knowledge, as well as compliance officers who usually have legal backgrounds, with limited technical know-how. These gaps are particularly obvious when new privacy-enhancing technologies need to be incorporated at the enterprise level, to ensure technical robustness and performance (utility) as well as compliance and ethical mandates (privacy).

A. Privacy Protection in the GDPR

The issue of privacy-utility balance using synthetic data is as much a technical challenge as it is a regulatory one.

Anonymization is the process of removing all personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that may lead to an individual being identified. Direct identifiers include name, address, telephone number, and photograph. At the same time, indirect identifiers refer to personal data that gives away identity when with other sources of information, including place of work, job title, salary, postcode, or health condition.

According to GDPR [9], anonymization is a process that transforms personal data into anonymous data “which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.”

If data is completely anonymous, it falls out of the GDPR scope, so many organisations strive to make the personal data in their environment anonymous using various methods.

Some of the more common anonymization methods are as follows:

- *Aggregation*: Data is displayed as totals, so no data relating to or identifying any individual is shown. Small numbers in totals are often suppressed through ‘blurring’ or omitted altogether.
- *Data masking*: This involves stripping out obvious personal identifiers, such as names, from a piece of information to create a data set in which no personal identifiers are present.
- *Data Perturbation*: the values from the original dataset are modified to be slightly different.
- *Data Permutation/Shuffling*: The purpose of swapping is to rearrange data in the dataset such that the individual attribute values are still represented in the dataset but, generally, do not correspond to the original records. This technique is also referred to as shuffling and permutation.
- *Suppression*: Record suppression refers to the removal of an entire record in a dataset.

Although these techniques are considered anonymization techniques, they do not necessarily produce GDPR-compliant anonymous data. For each of these techniques, there are documented reidentification risks like identity disclosure/singling out, linkage, and inference [10]. What GDPR means by anonymous data is that the risk of reidentification of an individual from that data is zero. The trouble with this is that it is practically impossible to achieve and assure 100% anonymity if one wants to derive an iota of value from the resulting anonymous dataset.

This is called the privacy-utility conundrum. The higher the privacy, the lower the utility, and vice-versa. This conundrum has brought a renewed focus on privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) to solve the gap.

PETs are digital solutions that allow the collection, analysis, and sharing of personal data while protecting confidentiality and privacy. Examples include, but are not limited to, secure multiparty computation, homomorphic encryption, zero-knowledge proofs, federated learning, secure enclaves, differential privacy, and synthetic data generation [11].

B. Synthetic Data as a PET

A study funded by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission has found that “Compared to other privacy-preservation techniques, synthetic data can have the best value/effort performance” [7].

There have already been a few impactful examples of synthetic data use cases for privacy preservation. The US Census Bureau [12] employs it in their public datasets and online tools to “balance the competing requirements of releasing statistics and protecting privacy”.

A research project commissioned by the city of Dubai [13] showed that differentially private-synthetic data outperforms traditional data anonymization techniques (such as removal, substitution, masking, and aggregation) in terms of protecting the privacy of individuals and boosting data utility (or usefulness). For a dataset containing traffic accidents, they almost completely protect individuals’ privacy while preserving 90% of the utility, as measured against the original dataset.

However, the mere generation of synthetic data alone does not guarantee privacy and can be susceptible to the reidentification risks of regular personal data [14].

Therefore all the generated synthetic data should have quantifiable privacy risks (differential privacy, for example). In addition to the qualitative data protection impact assessment, data controllers/privacy officers should perform a computational privacy assurance assessment to verify that the resulting synthetic data is not personal data. A synthetic dataset mirrors the original dataset, retaining its key properties such as attribute correlations, while simultaneously offering a verifiable privacy guarantee for individuals in the original dataset. This dual function ensures both privacy and utility features. [15].

C. Reidentification Techniques

Recent advancements in synthetic data generation have underscored the need for robust privacy evaluation mechanisms. The analysis of contemporary research reveals two significant challenges in this domain: the efficacy of membership inference attacks (MIAs) against synthetic data and the identification of vulnerable records within synthetic datasets.

- *Membership Inference Attacks*: given a synthetic dataset and a record, MIAs consist in establishing whether the record belongs to the original dataset from which the synthetic dataset was derived from. Guepin, et al. [16] demonstrate that MIAs can be effectively conducted using only synthetic data, challenging the prevailing assumption

that such attacks require auxiliary datasets similar to the training data. This finding points towards the inherent privacy risks in synthetic datasets and calls for the development of more secure synthetic data generation methods.

- *Vulnerable Record Identification*: Meeus, et al. [17] propose a novel methodology for identifying records within synthetic datasets that are particularly susceptible to MIAs. This method, which surpasses previous ad-hoc approaches, relies on assessing the closeness of synthetic records to their real counterparts. This approach enhances our ability to safeguard privacy in synthetic data publishing by providing a principled means of identifying and mitigating vulnerabilities.

From the perspective of regulation, The European Data Protection Supervisor’s report [18] provides an overview of emerging technologies that could impact data privacy and protection, especially on GDPR. It identifies key trends and technologies, such as synthetic data, as areas of growing interest and potential concern for data privacy regulations. The report underscores the need for tools and frameworks that can evaluate and ensure the privacy of synthetic data in light of evolving regulatory landscapes. In order to address these privacy risks, we propose a user-centric approach to assess privacy and utility of synthetic datasets within the complex, multi-user, and multi-stakeholder environment of an enterprise. This approach operates at the convergence of technology, business, and compliance.

III. USER-CENTERED METHODOLOGY

Following the introduction in Section I and a detailed analysis of privacy risks associated with synthetic data in Section II, Section III elaborates on the SURE project’s user-centered approach to software development. This section describes the integration of user stories and requirements identified through client needs gatherings, particularly within the financial, banking, and system integrator sectors.

A. User Engagement and Recruitment Process

For testing and validating our library we involved professionals of the sector, in line with the user-centered design proceedings.

The user engagement process, depicted in figure 1, begins with the user needs & persona identification phase. This crucial initial step successfully captures the specific needs, preferences, and characteristics of our target audience—data scientists and data protection officers—including user stories described in Section II. The project progresses into the recruitment and onboarding phase, with strategic recruitment efforts actively targeting participants who closely match the detailed personas previously identified. The SURE library is designed specifically for data scientist and regulatory professionals within large organizations, who possess a distinct combination of technical and legal expertise. Given this specialized profile, it is impractical to select our participants randomly from the general population. To ensure our validation process is

both effective and relevant, we plan to engage with 6-8 professionals who accurately represent our target user group

According to Nielsen [19], small groups of users can uncover up to 85% of usability issues, emphasizing the efficiency of this approach in iterative design processes. Additionally, Virzi [20] supports the effectiveness of small sample sizes in identifying the majority of usability problems, reinforcing the practicality of this strategy.

Our recruitment channels include valorizing our current business and community networks, as well as using social media to tap into first and second-degree connections. In addition, our desired user personas were recruited during a series of selected conferences and workshops on data privacy and synthetic data frequented by professionals with profiles in line with the user requirements.

Fig. 1. User engagement roadmap.

B. Testing and Validation

Once the users were recruited, we utilized two distinguished approaches for the two user personas for testing and validating our solution:

1) Data Scientists

Testing Approach: Data scientists test the SURE library by downloading it through our GitHub page. They use the library to evaluate synthetic data across various utility and privacy metrics, simulating real-world data handling scenarios.

Feedback Mechanism: Following the SURE library testing, data scientists are asked to complete a detailed feedback form that assesses the library’s functionality, ease of use, effectiveness, and any issues encountered or areas for improvement.

2) Data Protection Officers (DPOs)

Presentation Approach: DPOs attend a detailed presentation that outlines the capabilities and outputs of the SURE library, focusing on its compliance with GDPR and other privacy regulations. The presentation includes case studies, reports generated by the library, and discussions on potential use cases.

Feedback Mechanism: After the presentation, DPOs participate in a feedback session where they provide their insights, express concerns, and suggest enhancements from a compliance and regulatory perspective.

C. Feedback Analysis and Iterative Improvement

We use a combination of usability metrics and qualitative feedback, as discussed by Tullis and Albert [21], allows for a thorough assessment of both the functionality and compliance aspects of the library, ensuring that it meets industry standards

and user needs effectively. This feedback move into the analysis phase, where it is meticulously reviewed to draw actionable insights and identify prevalent themes. The feedback analysis focuses on evaluating user responses to pinpoint the library’s strengths and areas for improvement. Driven by insights from the feedback analysis, iterative improvements are made to the SURE library, targeting enhancements that address user-specific needs and issues identified. Adjustments may include updates to functionalities, user interface modifications, or compliance enhancements. Following these improvements, a final evaluation assesses their impact and effectiveness. The project wraps up with a comprehensive review that encapsulates the engagement outcomes, documenting key successes, challenges encountered, and providing strategic recommendations for future projects.

IV. SYNTHETIC DATA UTILITY AND PRIVACY ASSESSMENT

Established that synthetic data are not exempt from privacy attacks, the SURE library represents an effort to provide a comprehensive framework for their assessment, focusing on two critical dimensions: privacy and utility. By tackling these aspects through dedicated modules, the library aims to provide stakeholders with the tools required to measure and understand the implications of using synthetic data in diverse contexts.

The utility modules of the library are engineered to evaluate the informational value of synthetic data, particularly in the context of machine learning and data analytics tasks. They do so by assessing the degree of similarity between the original datasets and their synthetic counterparts, ensuring that the synthetic data retains the essential characteristics needed for effective data analysis and machine learning applications. These modules are crucial for organizations looking to leverage synthetic data for training machine learning models, as it provides insights into the data’s ability to support robust and accurate model development.

Conversely, the privacy modules are dedicated to quantifying the privacy risks associated with synthetic data. These modules employ advanced metrics and methodologies to identify and measure potential vulnerabilities that could lead to the reidentification of individuals or the exposure of sensitive information. By providing an understanding of privacy risks, the library empowers users to make informed decisions about the deployment of synthetic data, aligning with legal frameworks and ethical standards.

A. SURE’s Functionalities

The SURE library is available as an open-source Python library. All modules that make up the SURE library are available as Python classes or functions which can be easily integrated in any Python script.

The modules are conceived to ensure that their input arguments and their output seamlessly integrate and concatenate with one another. This design facilitates a fluid workflow, reported in figure 2, from the raw input datasets to the final privacy-utility report. Moreover, users have the flexibility to obtain intermediate results at each step, providing them with

Fig. 2. SURE’s modules overview and workflow

all the necessary instruments and information to maintain full control over every aspect of the process.

The main functionalities of the SURE library are reported below.

1) *Data ingestion, preparation and processing:* The library is compatible with different data infrastructures (databases, warehouse and data lakes) and data types. Initially we intend to apply the library to structured datasets and time-series aiming at extending its applicability to images. Such a library enhances flexibility and versatility in handling diverse datasets, regardless of their format or storage location. This means users can seamlessly process any kind of data without the need for multiple specialized tools. Data manipulation in the pre-processing module is performed using the library Polars, exploiting its optimization features to achieve blazing fast tabular data manipulation.

2) *Data utility evaluation:* Regarding the utility components the following tests are implemented.

Statistical Similarity Tests. These tests are devised to quantitatively compare the synthetic data with the original data in terms of statistical properties. They include:

- Descriptive statistics comparison, such as means, variances, distributional shapes and other quantities listed in table I.
- Correlation structures between variables to ensure that inter-variable relationships are preserved.
- Higher-order statistical tests to assess whether the synthetic data maintains the patterns and structures that exist

within the original data.

To facilitate direct comparison, all the aforementioned statistics are computed on both the original and the synthetic datasets.

TABLE I
STATISTICS COMPUTED ON THE DATASETS IN SURE.

<i>Feature type</i>		
Numerical	Categorical	Temporal
Null count	Null count	Null count
Num. of unique val.	Num. of unique val.	Num. of unique val.
Mean	Freq. of unique val.	Min
Std		Max
Min		Most freq. val.
First quartile		
Second quartile		
Third quartile		
Max		

Machine Learning Information Content. This set of tests measures the richness of information within the synthetic data from the perspective of machine learning models. The user can perform either a classification or a regression task on both the original and the synthetic dataset. It evaluates:

- The ability of the synthetic data to retain predictive qualities necessary for training machine learning models.
- Performance metrics when machine learning models trained on synthetic data are tested against holdout sets from the original data.
- The degradation, if any, in model accuracy, F1 score, ROC AUC, RMSE and other relevant metrics listed in table II when transitioning from original to synthetic data.

The user also has the option to add a custom metric.

TABLE II
MACHINE LEARNING METRICS COMPUTED BY SURE.

Classification	Regression
Accuracy	Adjusted R-squared
Balanced accuracy	R-squared
ROC AUC	RMSE
F1 score	

3) *Data privacy evaluation:* The privacy reports include the following analysis.

Distance Metrics. This analysis involves:

- Quantifying the 'closeness' of the individual synthetic records to real records employing Gower's distance [22] to ensure there is no one-to-one mapping that might lead to reidentification.
- Computing the share of records of the synthetic dataset that are closer to the training dataset than to the holdout dataset, an indicator of the vulnerability of the synthetic dataset.

Adversarial Privacy Robustness. This robustness check simulates an environment where the synthetic data is subjected to potential privacy attacks. It examines:

- The synthetic data's resilience to known privacy attack vectors, such as membership inference attacks, which attempt to deduce the presence of individual data points in the original dataset.
- The strength of the synthetic data against reconstruction attacks where attackers might use statistical methods to recreate individual entries from the synthetic data.

In this module, a simulated attacker is provided with partial information about the real dataset, referred to as the adversary dataset. Using this information and the synthetic data, the attacker attempts to determine whether the known records are part of the original dataset. This is achieved by either performing a machine learning classification task or computing the Gower's distance between the adversary dataset and the synthetic dataset. The module outputs a confidence probability for each record in the adversary dataset, indicating the likelihood that it belongs to the original dataset.

4) *Automatic report generation:* The library finally generates a clear and accessible privacy-utility report based on the outcomes of the modules described above. This visual digest is created in an HTML format and contains the relevant information needed to perform Data Privacy Impact Assessments and to evaluate the data utility performance of the synthetic dataset, ranging from statistical distribution similarity and distance based metrics to ML utility metrics. The report also shows the results of the privacy attack simulations carried out during assessment phase.

V. CONCLUSION

As AI continues to drive economic growth and innovation, the importance of ethical and privacy-conscious data practices becomes increasingly paramount. SURE's contribution to this domain, by providing a tool that balances the privacy-utility conundrum, is not just timely but essential.

By addressing key challenges through innovative methodologies for evaluating synthetic data, this initiative not only enhances the state of the art but also aligns with rigorous GDPR standards. Looking forward, the SURE library is set to empower data science professionals across various sectors, providing robust tools for informed decision-making regarding synthetic data use. Our efforts in SURE reiterate our commitment to advancing data science responsibly, ensuring privacy without compromising on utility.

The SURE project presents a modular architecture, allowing for flexible deployment and scalability and, most importantly, efficient iterative development. Each component, from data pre-processing to the report generation, has been meticulously structured to function either singularly or together through well-designed APIs.

In conclusion, the SURE project offers a significant step forward in addressing the complex challenges of balancing privacy with data utility in the field of AI. Through its comprehensive and user-centered approach of developing an open-source library, the SURE software toolkit not only enhances the capabilities of AI systems by providing privacy-preserving

synthetic data, but also ensures these systems are accessible, trustworthy, and regulatory-compliant.

As we submit this paper, the testing and validation phases are in progress. Looking ahead, the finalized version of SURE will be made available through a GitHub repository [23]. This open-source release will facilitate wider adoption and continuous improvement of the library, encouraging contributions from the global data science and privacy communities. Future work will focus on extending the library's capabilities to handle more diverse data types, including unstructured data.

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REFERENCES

- [1] PwC, "Sizing the prize: What's the real value of AI for your business and how can you capitalise?," *Price Waterhouse Coopers*, 2017. Available: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/analytics/assets/pwc-ai-analysis-sizing-the-prize-report.pdf>.
- [2] T. B. Brown, B. Mann, N. Ryder, M. Subbiah, J. D. Kaplan, P. Dhariwal, A. Neelakantan, P. Shyam, G. Sastry, A. Askell, and others, "Language models are few-shot learners," in *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 33, pp. 1877–1901, 2020.
- [3] A. Narayanan and V. Shmatikov, "Robust de-anonymization of large sparse datasets," in *2008 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (sp 2008)*, pp. 111–125, 2008. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2008.33>.
- [4] M. Fredrikson, S. Jha, and T. Ristenpart, "Model inversion attacks that exploit confidence information and basic countermeasures," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pp. 1322–1333, 2015. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2810103.2813677>.
- [5] S. Garfinkel, "NISTIR 8053: De-identification of personal information," *National Institute of Standards and Technology*, 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.IR.8053>.
- [6] P. Ram Mohan Rao, S. Murali Krishna, and A. P. Siva Kumar, "Privacy preservation techniques in big data analytics: a survey," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2018. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-018-0141-8>.
- [7] J. Hradec, M. Craglia, M. Di Leo, S. De Nigris, N. Ostlaender, N. Nicholson, "Multipurpose synthetic population for policy applications," EUR 31116 EN, *Publications Office of the European Union*, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-53478-5, doi:10.2760/50072, JRC128595, 2022. Available: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128595>.
- [8] D. Ghatak, K. Sakurai, "A Survey on Privacy Preserving Synthetic Data Generation and a Discussion on a Privacy-Utility Trade-off Problem." In: *Science of Cyber Security - SciSec 2022 Workshops*. SciSec 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1680. Springer, 2022.
- [9] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance) (OJ L 119 04.05.2016, p. 1).
- [10] J. Marques, J. Bernardino. "Analysis of Data Anonymization Techniques", On: *Proceedings of the 12th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management (IC3K 2020) - Volume 2: KEOD*, pages 235-241, 2020.
- [11] Office of Science and Technology Policy. "Request for Information on Advancing Privacy-Enhancing Technologies." vol. 2022-12432, no. 87 FR 35250, 2022, pp. 35250-35252, September 6 2022. Available: <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2022/06/09/2022-12432/request-for-information-on-advancing-privacy-enhancing-technologies>.
- [12] US Census Bureau, "What Are Synthetic Data?," May 27 2021, Available: <https://www.census.gov/about/what/synthetic-data.html>.
- [13] Digital Dubai, Synthetic Data Framework, "Unlocking the Power of Data and Protecting Privacy", October 6 2022. Available: <https://www.digitaldubai.ae/knowledge-hub/publications/synthetic-data>.
- [14] T. Stadler, B. Oprisanu, C. Troncoso, "Synthetic Data – Anonymisation Groundhog Day." In: *31st USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 22)*. USENIX Association, August 2022.
- [15] J. Near, D. Darais, "Differentially Private Synthetic Data." NIST - National Institute of Standards and Technology, May 2021..
- [16] F. Guépin, M. Meeus, AM. Crețu, YA. de Montjoye, "Synthetic Is All You Need: Removing the Auxiliary Data Assumption for Membership Inference Attacks Against Synthetic Data." In: *Computer Security. ESORICS 2023 International Workshops*. ESORICS 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14398. Springer, 2024.
- [17] M. Meeus, F. Guépin, AM. Crețu, YA. de Montjoye, "Achilles' Heels: Vulnerable Record Identification in Synthetic Data Publishing." In: *Computer Security – ESORICS 2023*. ESORICS 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14345. Springer, 2024.
- [18] European Data Protection Supervisor, "TechSonar 2021-2022 Report", December 20 2021. Available: https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/reports/techsonar-2021-2022-report_en.
- [19] J. Nielsen, "Usability Engineering," Academic Press, Inc., 1993.
- [20] R.A. Virzi, "Refining the test phase of usability evaluation: How many subjects is enough?" *Human Factors*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 457–468, 1992.
- [21] T. Tullis and B. Albert, "Measuring the User Experience: Collecting, Analyzing, and Presenting Usability Metrics," Newnes, 2013.
- [22] J.C. Gower, "A General Coefficient of Similarity and Some of Its Properties", In: *Biometrics*, Vol. 27, No. 4, pp. 857-871, 1971.
- [23] SURE library Github repository. Available: <https://github.com/Clearbox-AI/SURE>